

FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM OF EARTHQUAKE RESISTANCE OF MULTI-STOREY BUILDINGS BASED ON A PLATE MODEL

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the development of a continuum plate model of a multi-story building, the seismic vibrations of which are modeled by the movement of a thick orthotropic cantilever plate, the deformation of which is described on the basis of the bi-moment theory of thick plates. Formulas are presented for determining the reduced moduli of elasticity, shear and density of a plate model of a building. The maximum values of normal displacement and stress are calculated depending on three values of the frequency of external influence during forced transverse vibrations of a nine-story building during an earthquake of magnitude 8.

Key words: Multi-storey building, continuum plate model, reduced moduli of elasticity, shear and density, seismic impact, numerical method, maximum displacements and stresses.

1. Introduction

The development of dynamic spatial models of buildings and structures, the deformation of which is spatial in nature, is one of the complex current problems in the mechanics of a deformable body and the dynamics of structures. Various methods have been developed for calculating buildings and structures for seismic impacts, taking into account various important factors.

The article proposes a method for calculating multi-story buildings within the framework of a continuum plate model [1-4]. When determining the reduced density and elastic modulus of a plate model, we will use the technique developed in [3-5]. The building is believed to consist of numerous boxes (rooms). Note that the continuum plate model of a multi-story building was developed on the basis of the bi-moment theory of thick plates [6-8]. The movement of a multi-story building under seismic impacts is represented as transverse vibrations of a certain thick cantilever plate, which is deformed within the framework of the bi-moment theory of plates.

The reduced density of a building is determined by the following formula:

$$m_{\text{reduced}} = \rho_{\text{density}} V_1 = \rho_{\text{reduced}} V_0. \quad (1)$$

Here V_1 – volume of slabs forming one floor of a building. V_0 – volume of one floor of a building. Then, to calculate these volumes, we obtain the following formulas:

$$V_0 = ab_1H, V_1 = 2ab_1h_1 + ab_1h_2 + 2Hb_1h_1 + (n-2)Hb_1h_2 + aHh_{\text{overlap}}, \quad (2)$$

Here a, H – building length and width; b_1 – one floor height of the building; n – number of interior walls of the building; h_1 – outer wall thickness; h_2 – interior wall thickness; h_{overlap} – floor thickness.

In general, the elastic characteristics and densities of the spatial continuum model of a building are determined by the following formulas [1-4]:

$$\begin{aligned} E_1^{\text{reduced}} &= \zeta_{11}E_0, E_2^{\text{reduced}} = \zeta_{22}E_0, E_3^{\text{reduced}} = \zeta_{33}E_0, \\ G_{12}^{\text{reduced}} &= \zeta_{12}G_0, G_{13}^{\text{reduced}} = \zeta_{13}G_0, G_{23}^{\text{reduced}} = \zeta_{23}G_0, \\ \rho_{\text{reduced}} &= \rho_0\zeta_0. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Note that coefficient values $\xi_{11}, \xi_{22}, \xi_{33}, \xi_{12}, \xi_{13}, \xi_{23}, \zeta_0$ for each cell (room) of the discrete part of the building are defined as functions of two spatial variables, E_0, G_0 – elastic and shear modulus of the strongest cell support panel of the discrete part of the building.

Write down formulas for determining coefficients $\xi_{11}, \xi_{22}, \xi_{33}, \xi_{12}, \xi_{13}, \xi_{23}, \zeta_0$ given moduli of elasticity of a discrete part of the building in the form [1-4]:

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_{11} &= \alpha \frac{S_{11}}{S_{01}}, \quad \xi_{22} = \alpha \frac{S_{22}}{S_{02}}, \\ \xi_{33} &= \alpha \frac{S_{33}}{S_{03}}, \quad \xi_{12} = \alpha \frac{S_{12}}{S_{01}}, \\ \xi_{13} &= \alpha \frac{h_{nep}}{b_1} \lambda^*, \quad \xi_{23} = \alpha \frac{h_2}{a_1}, \quad \zeta_0 = \frac{V_1}{V_0}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Here S_{01}, S_{02}, S_{03} – area of cross-sections of the building in three coordinate planes of one floor of the building; S_{11}, S_{22}, S_{33} – total area of the cross sections of the plates in the coordinate planes forming one floor of the building; λ^* – coefficient characterizing the hollow cross-section of the slab. Coefficient α is determined according to the cellular structure of the building structure.

Note that the above volumes and areas are determined depending on the size of the plates, rooms and the building itself, as follows:

$$S_{01} = E_0 b_1 H, S_{02} = E_0 a H, S_{03} = E_0 a b_1, \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} S_{11} &= b_1 h_2 E_b^{(2)} + H h_{overlap} E_{overlap}, S_{12} = b_1 h_2 E_b^{(2)}, \\ S_{22} &= a h_2 E_b^{(2)} + (k - 2) H h_2 E_b^{(2)}, \\ S_{33} &= a h_2 E_b^{(2)} + (k - 2) b_1 h_2 E_b^{(2)} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Here G_{nep} – building slab displacement module; G_2 – interior wall shear module; $E_b^{(2)}$ – interior wall elastic module; E_{nep} – floor elastic module.

Now let's define the given modules of elasticity and shear of external walls, taking into account window openings, using the method given in [5] as approximate formulas:

$$\begin{aligned} E_1^{reduced} &= E_1 \left(1 - \frac{\eta}{\eta_0}\right), E_2^{reduced} = E_2 \left(1 - \frac{\eta}{\eta_0}\right), \\ G_{12}^{reduced} &= G_{12} \left(1 - \frac{\eta}{\eta_0}\right), G_{13}^{reduced} = G_{13} \left(1 - \frac{\eta}{\eta_0}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Here E_1, E_2, G_{12}, G_{13} – external wall flexibility and shear modules, η, η_0 – constant coefficients.

Thus, we have obtained formulas for representing the values of the reduced elasticity module of the plate model of the building.

Coefficient values $\xi_{11}, \xi_{22}, \xi_{33}, \xi_{12}, \xi_{13}, \xi_{23}, \zeta_0$ for each cell (room) of the building are defined as functions of two spatial variables, E_0, G_0 – elastic and shear modulus of the strongest load-bearing panel of the building.

Therefore, we have obtained formulas (1) - (8) to determine the reduced elasticity modules of the plate model of the building. According to the obtained formulas (1) - (8), the reduced elastic modules are 8-30 times smaller than the elastic module of the panels, and the reduced density of the plate model of the discrete part of the building is 7-20 times less than the material density of the panels, This is due to the cellular structure of the building with a large number of voids.

2. Problem formulation.

Now let's consider the asymmetric problem of the bimomental theory. Movement of dots plate model of multi-storey building is considered in Cartesian coordinate system x_1, x_2 and z . The origin of the coordinates is located in the lower left corner of the median surface of the continuum plate model of a multi-storey building. Direct the Ox_1 and Ox_2 axes along the length and height, and the Oz axis along the thickness (building width) of the plate model.

The asymmetric problem of bimomental plate theory consists of equations relative to bending and torque, cutting forces and bimomes relative to nine unknown kinematic functions, i.e.:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{u}_k &= \frac{u_k^{(+)} - u_k^{(-)}}{2}, \quad \tilde{\psi}_k = \frac{1}{2h^2} \int_{-h}^h u_k z dz, \\ \tilde{\beta}_k &= \frac{1}{2h^4} \int_{-h}^h u_k z^3 dz, \quad (k = 1, 2), \\ \tilde{W} &= \frac{u_3^{(+)} + u_3^{(-)}}{2}, \quad \tilde{r} = \frac{1}{2h} \int_{-h}^h u_3 dz, \\ \tilde{\gamma} &= \frac{1}{2h^3} \int_{-h}^h u_3 z^2 dz. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Cargo Terms of problem two equation $\tilde{q}_k, (k = 1, 2), \tilde{q}_3$ are defined as:

$$\tilde{q}_k = \frac{q_k^+ + q_k^-}{2}, \quad (k = 1, 2), \quad \tilde{q}_3 = \frac{q_3^+ - q_3^-}{2}. \quad (10)$$

For bending and torque moments M_{11}, M_{22}, M_{12} possess

$$M_{11} = \frac{H^2}{2} \left(E_{11} \frac{\partial \tilde{\psi}_1}{\partial x_1} + E_{12} \frac{\partial \tilde{\psi}_2}{\partial x_2} - E_{13} \frac{2(\tilde{r} - \tilde{W})}{H} \right),$$

$$M_{22} = \frac{H^2}{2} \left(E_{12} \frac{\partial \tilde{\psi}_1}{\partial x_1} + E_{22} \frac{\partial \tilde{\psi}_2}{\partial x_2} - E_{23} \frac{2(\tilde{r} - \tilde{W})}{H} \right),$$

$$M_{12} = M_{21} = G_{12} \frac{H^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{\psi}_1}{\partial x_2} + \frac{\partial \tilde{\psi}_2}{\partial x_1} \right) \quad (11)$$

Bending and Torque P_{11}, P_{22}, P_{12} will be written in:

$$P_{11} = \frac{H^2}{2} \left(E_{11} \frac{\partial \tilde{\beta}_1}{\partial x_1} + E_{12} \frac{\partial \tilde{\beta}_2}{\partial x_2} - E_{13} \frac{2(3\tilde{\gamma} - \tilde{W})}{H} \right),$$

$$P_{12} = P_{21} = \frac{H^2}{2} G_{12} \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{\beta}_1}{\partial x_2} + \frac{\partial \tilde{\beta}_2}{\partial x_1} \right),$$

$$P_{22} = \frac{H^2}{2} \left(E_{12} \frac{\partial \tilde{\beta}_1}{\partial x_1} + E_{22} \frac{\partial \tilde{\beta}_2}{\partial x_2} - E_{23} \frac{2(3\tilde{\gamma} - \tilde{W})}{H} \right). \quad (12)$$

Expressions for defining cutting forces are:

$$Q_{13} = G_{13} \left(2\tilde{u}_1 + H \frac{\partial \tilde{r}}{\partial x_1} \right),$$

$$Q_{23} = G_{23} \left(2\tilde{u}_2 + H \frac{\partial \tilde{r}}{\partial x_2} \right). \quad (13)$$

Cross-sectional bimoment intensity $\tilde{p}_{13}, \tilde{p}_{23}$ are constructed using tangent stresses σ_{13}, σ_{23} as:

$$\tilde{p}_{k3} = G_{k3} \left(\frac{2\tilde{u}_k - 4\tilde{\psi}_k}{H} + \frac{\partial \tilde{\gamma}}{\partial x_k} \right), \quad (k = 1, 2). \quad (14)$$

The normal bimoment $\tilde{p}_{33}$ intensity is constructed taking into account the expression of normal voltage σ_{33} in the form of:

$$\tilde{p}_{33} = E_{31} \frac{\partial \tilde{\psi}_1}{\partial x_1} + E_{31} \frac{\partial \tilde{\psi}_1}{\partial x_1} - E_{33} \frac{2(\tilde{r} - \tilde{W})}{H}. \quad (15)$$

The equations of motion of asymmetric deformation of the plate model of a multi-storey building are also described using a system of six equations.

The first three equations of motion of the plate model of a multi-storey building are obtained relative to bending, torque and cutting forces:

$$\frac{\partial M_{11}}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial M_{12}}{\partial x_2} - Q_{13} + H\tilde{q}_1 = \frac{H^2}{2} \rho \ddot{\tilde{\psi}}_1,$$

$$\frac{\partial M_{21}}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial M_{22}}{\partial x_2} - Q_{23} + H\tilde{q}_2 = \frac{H^2}{2} \rho \ddot{\tilde{\psi}}_2. \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{\partial Q_{13}}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial Q_{23}}{\partial x_2} + 2\tilde{q}_3 = \rho H \ddot{\tilde{r}}. \quad (17)$$

The next three equations of motion of the plate model of a multi-storey building will be recorded relative to the bimoment. Of these, the two equations relative to bending and torsional bimoment are:

$$\frac{\partial P_{11}}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial P_{12}}{\partial x_2} - 3H\tilde{p}_{13} + H\tilde{q}_1 = \frac{H^2}{2} \rho \ddot{\tilde{\beta}}_1,$$

$$\frac{\partial P_{21}}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial P_{22}}{\partial x_2} - 3H\tilde{p}_{23} + H\tilde{q}_2 = \frac{H^2}{2} \rho \ddot{\tilde{\beta}}_2. \quad (18)$$

The sixth equation of the motion of the plate model of a multi-storey building relative to the intensity of the transverse bimomenta will be recorded in the form of:

$$H \frac{\partial \tilde{p}_{13}}{\partial x_1} + H \frac{\partial \tilde{p}_{23}}{\partial x_2} - 4\tilde{p}_{33} + 2\tilde{q}_3 = H\rho \ddot{\tilde{\gamma}}. \quad (19)$$

From the above equations it can be seen that in the first problem of the bimoment theory of the plate, all formulas of forces, moments and bimoments and differential equations of motion (16) - (18) are constructed precisely and form a joint system of six equations with respect to nine unknown functions $\tilde{\psi}_1, \tilde{\psi}_2, \tilde{u}_1, \tilde{u}_2, \tilde{\beta}_1, \tilde{\beta}_2, \tilde{r}, \tilde{\gamma}, \tilde{W}$.

Generalized movements of the front surfaces $\tilde{u}_1, \tilde{u}_2$ for asymmetric problems are determined from the following equations:

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\sigma}_{11}}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial \tilde{\sigma}_{12}}{\partial x_2} + \frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{13}^*}{H} = \rho \ddot{\tilde{u}}_1, \quad \frac{\partial \tilde{\sigma}_{21}}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial \tilde{\sigma}_{22}}{\partial x_2} + \frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{23}^*}{H} = \rho \ddot{\tilde{u}}_2, \quad (20)$$

here moments $\tilde{\sigma}_{11}, \tilde{\sigma}_{12}, \tilde{\sigma}_{22}$ are determined by formula

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{11} = \left(E_{11} - \frac{E_{13}}{E_{33}} E_{31} \right) \frac{\partial \tilde{u}_1}{\partial x_1} + \left(E_{12} - \frac{E_{13}}{E_{33}} E_{32} \right) \frac{\partial \tilde{u}_2}{\partial x_2} + \frac{E_{13}}{E_{33}} \tilde{q}_3,$$

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{22} = \left(E_{21} - \frac{E_{23}}{E_{33}} E_{31} \right) \frac{\partial \tilde{u}_1}{\partial x_1} + \left(E_{22} - \frac{E_{23}}{E_{33}} E_{32} \right) \frac{\partial \tilde{u}_2}{\partial x_2} + \frac{E_{23}}{E_{33}} \tilde{q}_3,$$

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{12} = G_{12} \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{u}_1}{\partial x_2} + \frac{\partial \tilde{u}_2}{\partial x_1} \right). \quad (21)$$

The generalized normal movement of facial surfaces $\tilde{W}$ for asymmetric problems is determined from the following equations:

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{q}_1}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial \tilde{q}_2}{\partial x_2} + \frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{33}^*}{H} = \rho \ddot{\tilde{W}} \quad (22)$$

In equations (20) and (22) of bimoment intensity $\tilde{\sigma}_{13}^*, \tilde{\sigma}_{23}^*, \tilde{\sigma}_{33}^*$ are defined as:

$$\frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{31}^*}{H} = \frac{\tilde{q}_1 - \tilde{\sigma}_{13}}{\Delta H}, \quad \frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{32}^*}{H} = \frac{\tilde{q}_2 - \tilde{\sigma}_{23}}{\Delta H}, \quad \frac{\tilde{\sigma}_{33}^*}{H} = \frac{\tilde{q}_3 - \tilde{\sigma}_{33}}{\Delta H} \quad (23)$$

here

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{13} = G_{13} \left[\frac{7}{6} \frac{\partial \tilde{W}}{\partial x_1} + \frac{E_{31}}{E_{33}} \frac{H}{36} \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{u}_1}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{H}{36} \frac{E_{32}}{E_{33}} \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{u}_2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} - \frac{35(33\tilde{\beta}_1 - 9\tilde{\psi}_1 - 4\tilde{u}_1)}{6H} \right] -$$

$$\tilde{p}_{23} = 0, \tilde{\sigma}_{11} = 0, \tilde{\sigma}_{12} = 0, \sigma_{22}^* = 0. \quad (31)$$

$$-\frac{1}{6}\tilde{q}_1 - \frac{G_{31}}{E_{33}}\frac{H}{36}\frac{\partial\tilde{q}_3}{\partial x_1},$$

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{23} = G_{23} \left[\frac{7}{6}\frac{\partial\tilde{W}}{\partial x_2} + \frac{E_{31}}{E_{33}}\frac{H}{36}\frac{\partial^2\tilde{u}_1}{\partial x_2\partial x_1} + \frac{H}{36}\frac{E_{32}}{E_{33}}\frac{\partial^2\tilde{u}_2}{\partial x_2^2} - \frac{35(33\tilde{\beta}_2 - 9\tilde{\psi}_2 - 4\tilde{u}_2)}{6H} \right] - \frac{1}{6}\tilde{q}_2 - \frac{G_{32}}{E_{33}}\frac{H}{36}\frac{\partial\tilde{q}_3}{\partial x_2}, \quad (24)$$

$$\tilde{\sigma}_{33} = \frac{5E_{31}}{6}\frac{\partial\tilde{u}_1}{\partial x_1} + \frac{5E_{32}}{6}\frac{\partial\tilde{u}_2}{\partial x_2} + \frac{H}{36}\left(E_{31}\frac{\partial^2\tilde{W}}{\partial x_1^2} - E_{32}\frac{\partial^2\tilde{W}}{\partial x_2^2}\right) - E_{33}\frac{35(9\tilde{\gamma} - 2\tilde{W} - \tilde{r})}{6H} + \frac{1}{6}\tilde{q}_3 - \frac{H}{36}\left(E_{31}\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1}\left(\frac{\tilde{q}_1}{G_{13}}\right) + E_{32}\frac{\partial}{\partial x_2}\left(\frac{\tilde{q}_2}{G_{23}}\right)\right). \quad (25)$$

On the free sides of the building, we have zero forces, moments and moments and zero power factors:

$$M_{11} = 0, M_{12} = 0, P_{11} = 0, P_{12} = 0, Q_{13} = 0, \tilde{p}_{13} = 0, \tilde{\sigma}_{11} = 0, \tilde{\sigma}_{12} = 0, \sigma_{13}^* = 0 \quad (26)$$

On the free top of the building we have conditions:

$$M_{12} = 0, M_{22} = 0, P_{12} = 0, P_{22} = 0, Q_{23} = 0, \tilde{p}_{23} = 0, \tilde{\sigma}_{11} = 0, \tilde{\sigma}_{12} = 0, \sigma_{23}^* = 0 \quad (27)$$

Suppose that the seismic movement of the soil occurs in the direction of the Oz axis (the width of the building).

At the base of the plate model of a multi-storey building, the boundary conditions for bending-shear oscillations have the form of:

$$\tilde{\psi}_1 = 0, \tilde{\psi}_2 = 0, \tilde{\beta}_1 = 0, \tilde{\beta}_2 = 0, \tilde{u}_1 = 0, \tilde{u}_2 = 0, \tilde{r} = u_0(t), \tilde{\gamma} = \frac{1}{3}u_0(t), \tilde{W} = u_0(t) \quad (28)$$

here $u_0(t)$ – law of base motion.

On the free side faces of the plate model of a multi-storey building we have the conditions of equality of zero forces, moments and moments and power factors:

$$M_{11} = 0, M_{12} = 0, P_{11} = 0, P_{12} = 0, Q_{13} = 0, \tilde{p}_{13} = 0, \tilde{\sigma}_{11} = 0, \tilde{\sigma}_{12} = 0, \sigma_{11}^* = 0 \quad (30)$$

On the free top of the building we have conditions:

$$M_{12} = 0, M_{22} = 0, P_{12} = 0, P_{22} = 0, Q_{23} = 0,$$

Specifies zero initial conditions for the task.

3. Example

Set the external seismic effects, set the acceleration of $\ddot{u}_0(t)$ on the lower clamped edge as:

$$\ddot{u}_0(t) = a_0 \cos(\omega_0 t),$$

Here $a_0 = k_c g$, here k_c and g Coefficient of seismicity and acceleration of gravity fall, ω_0 frequency of ground oscillation.

From the expression of acceleration are defined the expressions of moving the base of the building as

$$u_0(t) = \frac{A_0}{2}(1 - \cos(\omega_0 t)).$$

Here A_0 – amplitude of movement of the soil foundation under seismic influence. To solve the problem numerically, the finite difference method was chosen. To approximate the derivatives of displacements along spatial coordinates, we will use the formulas of central difference schemes.

To obtain numerical results, the following initial data were used for the structures of the considered plate model of a multi-story building.

The results of calculations of forced vibrations of a building within the framework of a thick plate model for the following sizes of slabs and building are presented: $h_1 = 0.40m, h_2 = 0.25m, h_{\text{floor}} = 0.2m, a_1 = 6m, b_1 = 3m$, The length, height and width of the multi-storey building are assumed to be the same $a = 30m, b = 30m, H = 13m$.

Then the coefficients $\xi_0, \xi_{11}, \xi_{22}, \xi_{33}, \xi_{12}, \xi_{13}, \xi_{23}$ for formulae (3) and (6) take the following values:

$$\xi_0 = 0.167, \xi_{11} = 0.11, \xi_{22} = 0.14, \xi_{33} = 0.093, \xi_{12} = 0.077, \xi_{13} = 0.067, \xi_{23} = 0.041.$$

The modulus of elasticity and density of concrete are equal: $E = 20000MPa, \rho = 2700kg/m^3$; according to formulas (3), the characteristics of the building were equal

$$E_1^{\text{given}} = 1320MPa, E_2^{\text{given}} = 1640MPa, E_3^{\text{given}} = 1120MPa, G_{12}^{\text{given}} = 135MPa, G_{13}^{\text{given}} = 120MPa, G_{23}^{\text{given}} = 72MPa, \rho_{\text{given}} = 451kg/m^3.$$

Seismic and base acceleration rates are calculated as: $k_s=0.2$ и $\omega_0=1.8$ Hz. Unlimited variables introduced $x=x_1/a, y=x_2/b, \tau=c_i/H$, here $c = \sqrt{E/\rho}$.

4. Results

On figure. 1, 2 and table. 1 results of calculations for 9-storey building at 8-point earthquake depending on three values of frequency of external impact ν_0 in the case of forced transverse oscillations of a nine-storey building, for the value of the transverse size of the building $H = 13m$.

On the basis of the resonance method, the values of the eigenfrequency of the nine-story building were found depending on the values of the length, height and width of the building $a = 30m, b = 30m, H = 13m$. When determining the frequency p_1 of its own

vibration, the seismic frequency value ν_0 gradually increases from a given value to a resonance event.

It should be noted that seismic impact is determined by acceleration of the base with an amplitude of equal $a_0 = k_c g$ when $k_c=0.2$, which corresponds to the intensity of an 8-magnitude earthquake. Under a given seismic impact, forced vibrations characterized by beating are observed.

Based on the continuum plate model, numerical results of displacement and stress at characteristic points of a multi-story building were obtained during magnitude 8 earthquakes.

In Fig. Figure 1 shows graphs characterizing changes in the maximum normal displacement r of the upper floors of a nine-story building versus time t .

Timoshenko theory

Bimomental theory

Figure 2 - Graphs of voltage changes over time for a nine-story building. (H=13 m)

In Table 1 shows the maximum values of lateral displacement r depending on three values of the frequency of external influence ν_0 with forced transverse vibrations of a nine-story building during an earthquake of magnitude 8, for the value of the transverse dimension of the building $H = 13 m$.

Table1. Comparison of Timoshenko theory and bi-moment theory according to the maximum values of normal displacement r , and stress depending on three values of the frequency of external influence ν_0 during forced transverse vibrations of a nine-story building during an earthquake of magnitude 8.

№	H	k_c	p_1, Hz	ν_0, Hz	r, m		σ_{22}, MPa		
					min	max	min	max	
1.	13	0.2	2.3	0.287	-0.052	0.082	-12	18	Timoshenko theory
2.				0.305	0,062	0,091	-14	19	
3.				0.335	-0.110	0.130	-25	29	
1.				0.304	-0.062	0.090	-14	20	Bimomental theory
2.				0.318	-0.080	0.110	-18	24	
3.				0.351	-0.179	0.190	-39	43	

Calculations were performed in the Delphi environment.

5. Conclusions

The problem of forced vibrations of multi-story buildings under seismic influences is formulated and solved based on a continuous plate model of a multi-story building.

A methodology, algorithm and program for numerical calculation of the stress state of a multi-story building within the framework of a plate model using an explicit finite difference method scheme have been developed.

Numerical results of displacements and stresses in characteristic sections of plate elements of a multi-story building were obtained.

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